

Accession 8106 demonstrated seed heterogeneity based on seed characteristics, disease reaction, and restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP) analysis of selected lines. DNA from 14 derived lines was digested with the restriction enzyme EcoRV and probed with 23 RFLP markers. Markers RG554 and RG476 revealed polymorphisms between lines. The two polymorphic probes detected three and five

heterozygotes, respectively. This suggested that 8106 was segregating.

Thirty-three progeny of 8106 were inoculated with several Xoo strains per plant. We observed a range of reaction patterns in different progeny with some plants showing differential reaction consistent with the first experiment. For five of these plants, 15 progeny each were tested with PXO 80, PXO 112, and PXO 145. The differential reaction of some of the families was confirmed (Table 2).

The differentiation of Xoo strains by inoculation on derivatives of 8106 (designated "8106-R") suggests that race 5 may consist of more than one race. It further suggests that 8106-R contains a resistance gene not present in the differential set used for race typing of these strains. Further testing is required to determine whether the lines derived from acc. 8106 contain a novel resistance gene. □

Quantifying rice-leaf blast (Bl) genetic relationship via the receptivity factor

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Host-pathogen relationships, such as that of the rice-*Pyricularia grisea* pathosystem, have genetic as well as epidemiological components. The specificity of the association between rice and *P. grisea* may be estimated through the receptivity factor (RF).

We conducted three glasshouse experiments at IRRI during the 1990 wet and 1991 dry seasons using susceptible lowland cultivars IR50 and IR72, moderately resistant upland variety UPLRi-5, and resistant variety Kinandang Patong. Seeds were sown in plastic cups. One plant per cup was maintained and fertilized with the equivalent of 120 kg N/ha.

Twenty plants/variety were inoculated with PO6-6, a local isolate of *P. grisea*. Inoculum suspension was sprayed on slides coated with plain agar and placed on a rotating platform of an electrically operated spore-settling tower device. Samples of the slides were fixed on healthy test plant leaves (one slide per leaf) using a spore concentration of 1.5×10^5 /ml, 1 min spraying time, and 10 psi spraying pressure.

We counted the spores deposited on other slides to estimate deposition on leaves. This procedure was repeated at 10, 25, 40, and 55 d after sowing. Control plants were treated with sterile distilled water. Lesions on all inoculated leaves were assessed immediately after symptoms appeared.

1. RF values of blast-infected IR50, IR72, UPLRi-5, and Kinandang Patong (KP).

RF value per plant at different ages was estimated:

$$RF = \frac{\text{no. of lesions produced on the plant}}{\text{no. of spores deposited on the plant}}$$

RF values of the varieties studied were highest in IR50. IR72 and IR50 showed a trend of declining RF in which younger leaves showed high susceptibility to BI (Fig. 1). UPLRi-5 produced a significantly different RF trend as leaves aged:

2. Linearized RF values of IR50 and IR72.

seedlings at 25 DAS showed more susceptibility to the disease than at any other age. Kinandang Patong was not infected at all.

IR50 was more susceptible than IR72 to BI at all ages studied. RF in IR72 decreased faster relative to IR50 as crops aged (Fig. 2). Both varieties are considered susceptible to BI. Our results suggest, however, that virulent pathogen isolates would cause more damage to IR50 than IR72 under field conditions favoring polycycles. RF values seem essential to accurately classify degrees of varietal resistance to *P. grisea*. □

Pest resistance—insects

Yield loss due to major rice pests in Tamil Nadu, India

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We assessed the yield loss caused by gall midge (GM) *Orseolia oryzae* (Wood-Mason) Mani, yellow stem borer (YSB)

Scirpophagu incertulas Walker, and leafhopper (LF) *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* Guenee on five rice varieties at Agricultural College and Research Institute, Madurai, during 1988-89. IR20, ADT36, MDU3, Sona, and IET9689 were raised under irrigated transplanted conditions during Jun-Sep and Oct-Jan.

We calculated yield loss for infestation at tillering, panicle initiation, and maturity (see table). IR20 suffered

Yield loss per unit increase in damage by GM, YSB, and LF in five rice varieties at 3 growth stages during 2 seasons.^a Madurai, India, 1988-89.

Variety	Yield loss (%)					
	Tillering		Panicle initiation		Maturity	
	Season I	Season II	Season I	Season II	Season I	Season II
<i>Gall midge (GM)</i>						
IR20	9.0	14.0	4.0	3.0	–	–
ADT36	1.0	3.0	2.5	2.0	–	–
MDU3	0.5	1.0	0.5	1.0	–	–
Sona	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	–	–
IET9689	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	–	–
<i>Yellow stem borer (YSB)</i>						
IR20	3.0	8.0	2.0	7.0	1.0	13.0
ADT36	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	2.0	2.0
MDU3	0.5	1.0	0.5	1.0	0.5	1.0
Sona	1.0	2.0	2.0	4.0	1.0	1.0
IET9689	8.0	1.0	12.0	1.0	4.0	2.0
<i>Leafhopper (LF)</i>						
IR20	2.0	2.0	3.0	3.0	10.0	10.0
ADT36	5.0	14.0	3.0	13.0	7.0	10.0
MDU3	4.0	6.0	3.5	3.0	4.0	2.0
Sona	2.0	4.0	4.0	4.0	0.5	1.5
IET9689	5.0	0.5	1.5	0.5	3.0	1.0

^aSeason I = Jun-Sep 1988, season II = Oct 1988-Jan 1989.

maximum loss from GM infestation in both seasons. GM-resistant MDU3 suffered the least damage from GM and YSB.

YSB caused heavy losses during the second season in all varieties except

IET9689, which suffered more during the first season. LF incidence accounted for heavy loss in ADT36 and MDU3 during early crop growth stages and in IR20 at later stages. □

Resistance to rice thrips in breeding lines derived from *Oryza officinalis*

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Fifty breeding lines derived from *O. officinalis* were exposed to natural infestation by thrips *Stenchaetothrips biformis* (Bagnall) during August 1990 at the ACRI, Killikulam.

Each breeding line was sown in 3 rows of 5 m each and susceptible TN1 and resistant Ptb 21 were sown at random. The breeding lines were not replicated in the preliminary screening test. When the susceptible TN1 showed a rating of 9, all breeding lines were rated for thrips damage using 0-9 scale. Breeding lines that showed a damage rating of 1 in the preliminary screening test were retested in a randomized block design replicated five times. Damage

rating was done as described. Of the 50 breeding lines evaluated for thrips resistance, 17 lines exhibited high levels of resistance (see table). □

Resistance to thrips in breeding lines derived from *O. officinalis*.

Breeding line	Damage rating ^a
IR54742-1-20-10-11-2	1.0 a
IR54742-4-7-9-7-1	1.0 a
IR54742-6-1-14-15-1	1.0 a
IR54742-6-1-14-15-3	1.0 a
IR54742-6-20-9-3-1	1.0 a
IR54742-6-20-9-3-2	1.0 a
IR54742-6-34-17-11-1	1.0 a
IR54742-18-17-20-15-2	1.0 a
IR54742-22-14-24-22-2	1.0 a
IR54742-22-14-24-22-3	1.0 a
IR54742-22-19-3-7-1	1.0 a
IR54742-22-19-3-7-2	1.0 a
IR54742-22-19-3-7-3	1.0 a
IR54742-33-18-20-3-5	1.0 a
IR54742-52-10-17-8-1	1.0 a
Ptb 21	1.0 a
TN1	9.0 b

^aMean of 5 replications. Scored using the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (0.9). Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

Reaction of summer and winter rice cultivars to hispa in Assam, India

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Hispa *Dicladispa armigera* (Oliv.) (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae) is a serious endemic rice pest in Assam. Fifty ahu (summer) rice cultivars from the Regional Agricultural Research Station, Titabor, Assam, were grown for 1 yr in earthen pots (40 cm diam, 36 cm deep) to screen for hispa resistance.

Pots containing ten 30-d-old seedlings each were randomly spaced at 20 × 15 cm in a 10-m² area surrounded by a white, mosquito-proof nylon net (15 × 15 × 2.5 m). Each cultivar had four replications (pots). About 14,000 field-collected adults were starved for 8 h and then released inside the net at 10/plant.

Saket 4 and Culture 1 were used as susceptible checks for summer and winter rice. Percent hispa-damaged leaves were recorded on three plants randomly selected from each replication of each variety 48 h after Saket-4 suffered 100% leaf damage.

Saket 4, Ratna, recommended modern varieties in Assam, and Culture 1 suffered more than 90% leaf damage. Eleven entries were moderately resistant

Reaction of summer and winter rice cultivars to hispa under nethouse conditions. Jorhat, Assam, India.

Variety	Leaf damage ^a (%)
<i>Summer rice</i>	
As 75	12.8
As 48	14.2
Govind	14.6
Bijer 3	15.0
Bengaubisi	15.1
As 36	16.5
Gareni	16.8
As 36/20	17.1
As 93/1	18.1
As 36/14	18.5
Mala	19.6
<i>Winter rice</i>	
Boro 1	12.5
IET10896	14.2
Govind	15.4
IET10898	15.9
IET10895	16.9

^aAv of 1989 and 1990.